

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL AND PRACTICAL COMPETENCE OF WOMEN ON THE BASIS OF QUALIFICATIONS

Magdieva Markhabo Erkinovna

Teacher at Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami.

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Abstract. *Studying the development of professional and practical competence of women based on teacher qualifications necessitates the identification of its structural components, as well as a description of their content. The specifics of teachers' professional competence are determined by the characteristics of pedagogical work and its differences from other types of activity.*

Keywords: *cognitive activity, immediate analysis and immediate action, pedagogical perception, pedagogical innovation.*

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Several differences can be identified:

1. The operational and systematic nature of pedagogical work requires, according to A.S. Makarenko, "immediate analysis and immediate action" [1-3].

2. Limited possibilities for reliably choosing the best option for solving a problem situation.

3. Pedagogical work is carried out constantly, day after day, but its results do not appear immediately; the property of "remote" effectiveness appears.

4. An essential professional feature of a teacher's work is the ability to predict further opportunities for developing the qualities of those being educated based on the primary results of influence.

5. Each teacher works individually, but, at the same time, the results of training and education are made up of the collective efforts of different teachers. Often, the lack of unity of requirements in the teaching staff can significantly reduce the effectiveness of the work of individual teachers.

6. An effective pedagogical process is determined by the integrity of the efforts of each of its participants (teachers, students and their parents, administration).

7. The work of a teacher is internally contradictory; it combines specialized knowledge, abilities, skills (in certain disciplines, branches of science and production) and general professional - psychological and pedagogical knowledge, abilities, skills. In addition, such internal heterogeneity of the teaching profession significantly complicates the comparison of the level of professional competence for different groups of teachers, especially requiring a differentiated approach [7, p. 29-31].

V.Ya. Adolf identifies the following special criteria for professional competence: 1. Selectivity. It is characterized by the degree of acceptance of pedagogical goals that are professionally and personally significant for the individual. Subjectively, this is manifested in a

differentiated reflection of goals in pedagogical activity, which determines the individual's desire to realize himself as a teacher already during the period of study at the institute. 2. Awareness. This refers to the ability of teachers to purposefully manage their mental activity and master the methods of competent analysis of professional situations. The acquired knowledge must be understood in a broader social context. 3. Effectiveness. It manifests itself in specific results of activities related to the pedagogical transformation of problem situations, in the degree of discrepancy between "should" and "desired". 4. Creative character. It is determined by the ability to transform non-standard pedagogical situations for socially and personally significant purposes, and to find optimal options for solving them. 5. Interest. It is necessary to combine personal and professional interests [6]. According to V.Ya. Adolf, the decisive influence on the structure of professional competence in accordance with its goals in the professional training system is exerted by: - the structure of cognitive activity; - the structure of the total object of study - the reality surrounding a person, reflected in the subject structure of scientific knowledge; - the need and specificity of specific types of cognitive activity; - the need to develop positive individual personality traits (abilities, interests, inclinations); - logic of development of the main parallels of the educational process [6].

It is important to note that none of these determinants can be placed above the others - all these factors collectively and comprehensively influence the structure of professional competence. Hence, the main components of the structure of professional competence, in the author's opinion, are: content-operational, motivational, goal-setting, personal [5, p. 66]. The structure of professional competence of V.A. Slastenin proposes to reveal through a set of general and specific professional skills. Ideally, full compliance of a specialist with the requirements of the qualification characteristics means the formation of a person who integrates the entire set of professional skills.

Djumaev M.I considering the professional competence of a school director, identifies the following functionally interconnected components: - motivational - a set of motives that are adequate to the goals and objectives of management; - cognitive – the body of knowledge necessary for management; - operational – a set of skills and abilities for practical problem solving; - personal – a set of personal qualities important for management; - reflexive – a set of abilities to anticipate, evaluate one's own activities, and choose a management strategy [9, p. 59].

The identification of these components is based on the following theoretical principles: - in its essence and structure, the professional competence of a school director includes main components that are closely related to the main structural elements of the management process; - such competence is not just a mechanical reflection of the management process, but is closely related to the "I-concept" of the school director - the totality of his ideas about himself, attitudes towards himself (reflection); - in each of the components of the structure of professional competence of the school director, qualities are presented that belong to both the first and second levels of management, and, accordingly, professional competence in this case is considered as an integral structure, in the unity of all its elements; - taking into account the peculiarities of management in the secondary education system, a special place among the qualities that belong to the second level (managerial decision-making, influencing people, taking into account the needs, motives, interests of workers, communication, etc.) will be given to personal formations related with a humanistic orientation of management [8].

According to the author, this model is universal, so it can be used to describe the professional competence of a teacher, a class teacher, and other representatives of the teaching profession. Differences in these descriptions will stem from the specific situations in which these specialists operate. In other words, if it is necessary to assess the competence of any specialist, it is necessary to determine not only the subjective, but also the real context of his actions. The specific situation in which he acts directly affects both the development of already formed and the mastery of new competence.

Based on this, the formation of professional competence among school directors was carried out by Djumaev M.I on the basis of their solutions to various types of management situations, namely: typical management situations common to the activities of managers of traditional and new types of educational institutions; typical management situations characteristic of the activities of heads of new types of schools (gymnasiums, lyceums); organizational, managerial and psychological situations in the activities of school leaders[9].

T.V. Dobudko describes the structure of a teacher's professional competence through certain types of skills, namely: 1. Analytical skills; 2. Predictive skills and projective skills; 3. Reflective skills (professional approach), as well as professional education adequate to them: - pedagogical thinking and pedagogical erudition; - pedagogical foresight, inference, imagination, intuition, forecasting; - pedagogical reflection [38, p. 200]. It should be noted that T.V. Dobudko investigated the problem of developing the professional competence of a teacher teaching a specific academic subject (computer science teacher). Within the framework of this study, we are talking about the pedagogical competence of the teacher in principle, and not the subject teacher. In the structure of professional competence of a teacher A.K. Markova identifies four blocks: 1. Professional (objectively necessary) psychological and pedagogical knowledge; 2. Professional (objectively necessary) pedagogical skills; 3. Professional psychological positions, teacher attitudes required of him by his profession; 4. Personal characteristics that ensure the teacher's mastery of professional knowledge and skills [10-11]. In the work of N.E. Kostyleva presents the following components of a teacher's professional competence: - personal-humanistic orientation; - pedagogical perception; - pedagogical skills; - pedagogical creativity. They are connected and form an integral system, based on which the author defines the professional competence of a teacher as a complex individual psychological formation, which is based on the integration of experience, theoretical knowledge, practical skills and significant personal qualities that determine the teacher's readiness for the actual implementation of pedagogical activity [12].

In the most general form, psychological and pedagogical knowledge is determined by curriculum. Psychological, pedagogical and special (subject) knowledge is a necessary, but far from sufficient condition for professional competence. Many of them, in particular theoretical, practical and methodological knowledge, are a prerequisite for pedagogical skills. Pedagogical skills are a set of pedagogical actions that consistently unfold in the external or internal plane, some of which can be automated (skills), aimed at solving the problems of developing a harmonious personality and based on relevant theoretical knowledge.

There are several approaches to classifying teaching skills. They can be reduced into three large groups: according to pedagogical functions [6]; on setting and solving various classes of pedagogical problems [12]; according to the stages of managing the pedagogical process [9]. As a result, the model of a teacher's professional competence can be presented as the unity of his

theoretical and practical readiness. Based on these approaches, pedagogical skills are combined into four groups: - constructive - the ability to set pedagogical tasks.

They are associated with the “translation” of the content of the objective process of socialization into specific tasks of training and education: studying the individual and the team in order to determine the level of preparedness for the active mastery of new knowledge and designing on this basis the development of the team and individual students; identifying a set of educational, educational and developmental tasks, their specification and determination of the dominant task; - organizational – the ability to program the method of pedagogical action. They make it possible to build and set in motion a logically complete pedagogical system: comprehensive planning of educational and developmental tasks; reasonable selection of the content of the educational process; optimal choice of forms, methods and means of its organization; - communicative – the ability to perform a pedagogical action.

They involve identifying and establishing the relationship between the components and factors of education and training, putting them into action: creating the necessary conditions (material, moral-psychological, organizational, hygienic, etc.) for the implementation of the educational process; development of the student’s activity, transforming him from an object into a subject of the pedagogical process; organization and development of joint activities; ensuring the connection of the school with the environment, regulating external non-programmable influences; - Gnostic – the ability to study the results of solving a problem. They require taking into account and evaluating the results of teaching activities: self-analysis and analysis of the progress of the pedagogical process and the actions of the teacher; defining a new set of dominant and subordinate pedagogical tasks. Pedagogical competence will only be a set of professional skills if it is not infused with pedagogical creativity. Without co-creation with students, a productive process is unthinkable.

In this regard, the approach to co-creation is interesting - highlighting a number of levels of co-creation: - the level of elementary interaction with the class: the teacher uses feedback, adjusts his influences based on its results, but he acts “according to a manual”, “according to a template”, based on the experience of other teachers ; - the level of optimization of activity in the lesson, starting with its planning, when creativity is manifested in a skillful choice and appropriate combination of content, methods and forms of teaching already known to the teacher; - heuristic, when the teacher uses the creative possibilities of live communication with students; - the highest level of co-creativity of the teacher, which is characterized by his complete independence; when using ready-made techniques, he puts a personal element into them, so they correspond to his creative individuality, the characteristics of the student’s personality, and the specific level of development of the class [7, p. 35-36]. The author also considers the issue of the relationship between the concepts of “pedagogical skill”, “pedagogical skill”, “pedagogical innovation” and “professional competence”.

Under the pedagogical skill of M.I Djumaev understands that the teacher has a fairly good command of the system of the most important teaching and educational skills, which in their totality allow him to carry out teaching and educational activities at the programmatic professional level and achieve more or less successful training and education of students. The next stage of professional growth and improvement of a teacher is pedagogical skill. Pedagogical skill is nothing more than teaching and educational skill brought to a high degree of perfection, which reflects the special polishing of methods and techniques for applying psychological and pedagogical theory in

practice, which ensures high efficiency of the educational process. The highest level of professional activity of a teacher is pedagogical innovation. Pedagogical innovation organically includes the promotion and implementation of new, progressive ideas, principles and techniques in the process of teaching and upbringing and a very significant increase in their quality[4-9].

According to the author, the frequently used categories “Pedagogical skill”, “Pedagogical skill”, “Pedagogical creativity” are not so much one-line, but can act as qualitative characteristics of teachers’ qualification levels. During the study, the author set the task of determining the relationship between professional competence, teaching skill and pedagogical creativity and developing the most complete indicators of these connections.

So, pedagogical skill is the activity of a teacher at the level of samples and standards, worked out in practice and already described in methodological developments and recommendations. The skill of a teacher is not directly related to his work experience. In contrast to mastery, pedagogical creativity is always a search and discovery of something new: either for oneself (the teacher’s discovery of variable, non-standard ways of solving pedagogical problems), or for oneself and for others (the creation of new original approaches to individual techniques that reconstruct known pedagogical experience).

Creativity, creative activity is an activity that generates something qualitatively new and distinguished by uniqueness, originality and socio-historical uniqueness. Thus, we can conclude that skill is part of pedagogical creativity and is a component of professional competence. Pedagogical competence in the areas: methodological foundations of pedagogy; pedagogical theories; pedagogical technology and methodology; design and construction of pedagogical systems; pedagogical communication; educational innovations; theories and practices of educational research; education management; professional self-improvement; management of a person’s mental state; psychological typologies[14-16]. Thus, in domestic psychology, the structural components of a teacher’s professional competence are determined either through a hierarchy of knowledge, skills, personal qualities, or through a number of specific abilities that presuppose professional skill, or through certain components, etc.

In foreign psychology, when determining professional competence, the emphasis is on the ability to act independently and responsibly. The main components of professional competence are: - social competence as the ability for group activities and cooperation with others, willingness to take responsibility for the results of one’s work, mastery of professional training techniques; - special competence – preparedness to independently perform specific types of activities, the ability to solve professional standard tasks and evaluate the results of one’s work, the ability to independently acquire new knowledge and skills in the specialty; - individual competence – readiness for constant improvement of qualifications and self-realization in professional work, the ability for professional reflection, overcoming professional crises and deformations. Thus, the development of the activity component of a teacher’s professional competence is most influenced by the first group of factors - a change in the leading activity (a change in the leading activity, a change in the way of performing an activity, improving the way of performing an activity).

The development of the socio-communicative component is influenced by the second group of factors - changes in the social situation of development (changes in the socio-economic situation, changes in the implementation of professional plans, innovative educational environment, random events, etc.). The development of the personal component is determined by the third group of factors - human subjectivity (increased social and professional activity, readiness

for professional self-determination, desire for self-development and self-realization, subjective feeling of stagnation in development).

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